

TECHNOLOGY OF ORGANIZATION, MAINTENANCE AND SEASONAL USE OF INTENSIVE FARMS.

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ABSTRACT

By creating intensive farms organized under a special worm house, the cost of growing cocoons is reduced, avoiding the costs of leaf transportation. The main thing is that silkworm rearing is taken out of the households of the villagers, this is considered a big social issue, and a certain part of the population is provided with work. It is also provided with a sufficient level of water and a clean food base to feed the cocoon.

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Figure 1. General view and development of the intensive nursery established near the special worm house

Figure 2. Irrigation of food orchards and application of agrotechnical measures.

Newly built silkworm rearing facilities in special feedlot areas are subject to land tax, property tax, uniform land tax, and compensation for agricultural and forestry production deficits. from payments on;

On the basis of the right of free use by JSC "Uzpakhtasanoat" to the organizations within the "Uzbekipaksanoat" association, the constructions intended for rearing silkworms were exempted from the profit tax calculated on land, property and rent of the tenant.

The decision also approved the parameters for establishing new mulberry plantations.

In particular, in addition to the existing 43,332 hectares of mulberry plantations, new mulberry plantations will be established on an area of 6,430 hectares this year, and 306 silkworm breeding facilities will be built.

It was created and recommended for production by scientists of the Scientific Research Institute of Silk Production of Uzbekistan in the establishment of a bush tutzor in an intensive way.

Intensive method 0.9 x 0.9 m. It is recommended to organize a trap in the scheme. 12,346 saplings are planted per hectare of tutzore created in this way. Hybrid saplings of mulberry or grafted variety seedlings are used in the establishment of such mulberry groves. Mulberry seedlings are planted in spring or autumn. For the establishment of an intensive method of planting, free from other types of seedlings, supplied with water, i.e. irrigated, flat, underground water is located 1.5-2 m below and in autumn (October-November) A plowed land area is separated at a depth of 30-35 cm.

Figure 3. Preparation of an irrigated, flat, and plowed land area to a depth of 30-35 cm in autumn (in October-November) for the establishment of an intensive method.

These works are carried out before the beginning of frosts and rains. In the areas where the rocky layer is close to the surface, the plowing depth is reduced to 22-25 cm. In autumn or spring, before planting saplings in the field, the field is leveled, chiseled to a depth of 20-22 cm, at the same time it is harrowed and ground with the help of an appropriate device,

after which the rows for planting seedlings or seedlings should be marked.

Complex agrotechnical methods are used in preparation of saline lands for planting, these works are carried out during the washing of salt of the earth and as recommended for different natural and geographical regions.

Figure 4. In autumn or spring, before planting seedlings in the field, the field is leveled and fertilized using this device

Figure 5. After the land area is leveled, plowed and plowed, rows for planting saplings or seedlings are determined.

Agrotechnics of intensively planted bush mulberry cultivation.

First-grade seedlings or substandard hybrid seedlings are planted to create bushes. After the lines for planting seedlings are determined, sprouts and seedlings are planted in the fall after

Khazan-rez or in early spring. When seedlings are planted in autumn, their root neck should be 4-5 cm below the surface of the earth, and when planted in spring, it should be 2-3 cm below the surface of the earth.

Figure 6. Procedure for planting sprouts or seedlings in designated rows.

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